

Comparing health impacts of dental amalgam with alternative restorative materials

Historically, dental amalgam—a combination of liquid mercury and a powdered alloy of silver, tin, and copper—has been widely used for dental restorations.³ However, due to concerns over mercury's toxicity and its potential risks to human health and the environment,^{3,4} the use of amalgam has continued to decline in the last 10 years.⁵ Other direct restorative materials (e.g. resin composites and glass ionomers) are now more frequently used, but their health and environmental impacts are not yet fully understood.

This systematic review was commissioned by the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) prior to the Conference of the Parties to the Minamata Convention on Mercury (COP-6). The review aimed to compare the health and environmental impacts of amalgam to other direct restoration materials,⁶ intending to support and inform decisions on the future use of dental amalgam within the UK.

Key findings from the 195 studies evaluating **health impacts** include:

- ◆ The quantity of evidence directly comparing the health of amalgam with other materials was limited.
- ◆ The number of non-comparative studies evaluating the impacts of amalgam or mercury far exceeded those evaluating other types of material.
- ◆ The health impact of occupational or maternal exposure to non-amalgam restorative materials has not been studied.
- ◆ Whilst few significant differences between treatment groups were observed across broad impact categories, the limited quantity of comparative evidence means we cannot be confident that there is no significant difference in health impact between amalgam and composite materials.
- ◆ Whilst some differences between the health impact of amalgam versus resin based composite were found for neuropsychological and psychosocial symptoms, one type of restorative material was not consistently better than the other.

Dental restorations are among the most common medical procedures performed globally,¹ with dental caries (tooth decay) being one of the major reasons for direct dental restorations.^{1,2}

How did we do this review?

Finding evidence: We searched databases which included health care and environmental science journals. We conducted backwards/forwards citation chasing and checked reviews and Google Search.

Eligibility criteria: Health and environmental impacts of materials used for direct dental restorations. Studies from high-income countries, published in English from 2007 onwards.

Study de-prioritization: We did not quality appraise or synthesize studies: 1) Only reporting exposure outcomes not directly related to health impact, 2) Where link between dental restorative material and health impact not primary focus, 3) Of cross-sectional design with/without comparison group.

Synthesis: We narratively synthesized health impacts by grouping studies according to type of restorative material, then dividing studies by population group (where applicable) and broad health impact evaluated.

Research question: What are the health impacts of direct dental restorations made of amalgam compared to other direct restorative materials?

Overview of the evidence

Dental material evaluated	N prioritised studies
Amalgam vs Resin based composite (Patients only)	6
Amalgam only	52
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients Dental professionals Maternal exposure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 36 7 10
Resin based composite only	16
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dental professionals Patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 15
Glass ionomer vs Resin based composite (Patients only)	3

We prioritised **61 studies** (87 articles) for synthesis.

18 of 25 broad **health impact categories** were supported by evidence from >1 category of restorative material. The most common type of health impacts evaluated included **Allergy** (n=13), **General physical health** (n=14), **Musculoskeletal** (n=10), **Neurological** (n=13), **Neuropsychological** (n=15), **Oral health** (n=18) and **Psychosocial** (n=13).

The quantity of evidence **directly comparing** health impacts of amalgam with those of composite resin was limited, relying heavily on articles reporting the **New England Children's Amalgam** and **Casa Pia** trials.

Study quality

16 studies were rated as strong quality, 18 studies as moderate quality and 26 studies rated as weak quality.

What did we find? - Health impacts

Amalgam vs Resin Based Composite

Broad health impacts with the highest quantity of data statistically comparing amalgam with RBC restorations included immune function, neuropsychological, oral health and psychosocial symptoms, although confidence in reported findings is limited due to moderate-weak evidence quality, heterogeneity of health impacts within specific categories and/or small number of studies.

Amalgam only

Restorations in situ/restoration removal in patients (36 studies): Heterogeneity in measures of amalgam exposure/health impacts and weak quality evidence prevented firm conclusions being drawn regarding the impact of amalgam on patient health.

Occupational exposure for health professionals (7 studies): Few consistent significant associations between mercury and health impacts found in individual health categories.

Maternal exposure (10 studies): ADHD/Autism (n=2): No firm conclusions regarding association between child autism/ADHD following maternal exposure.

Neuropsychological (n=3): Maternal exposure may impact child overall cognitive ability with some sex differences, but study heterogeneity limits conclusions.

Pregnancy impacts (n=7): No association between maternal amalgam exposure and childhood death for non-occupationally exposed mothers. Further research required into miscarriage risk for individuals with higher amalgam exposure. Tentative evidence suggests no association between maternal exposure and birth malformations, but the small quantity of low quality studies limit confidence in this finding.

Resin Based Composite only

Strongest evidence focused on neuro- and/or psychological impact and stemmed from three articles associated with the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. Only a few associations were found between composite resin and performance on psychological tests and greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial health at follow-up.

Glass Ionomer vs RBC/Compomer

Study designs, outcomes of interest and findings were heterogeneous, precluding identification of any clear conclusions regarding which restorative material was least detrimental to health.

What are the implications of this review?

This systematic review aimed to inform and support decision making around the future use of dental amalgam. Key implications include:

Policy makers:

- ◇ Findings from this review may be used in conjunction with other research and discussions from the Minamata COP-6 to support UK government policy regarding future use of amalgam.

Future research:

- ◇ Further high-quality research is required to fully understand the health impacts of different types of material both individually and compared to one another.
- ◇ There are comparatively fewer studies evaluating the health impacts of **resin based composite** and **glass ionomer** restorative materials across all population groups which should be addressed, particularly given current UK public health policy directing the phasing down of amalgam use.
- ◇ Further high-quality trials evaluating the potential health impacts associated with **resin based composite** would be beneficial. Particular health impacts include adverse events, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, respiratory and visual ocular symptoms. Health impacts associated with **occupational and maternal exposure** to glass ionomer or composite resin restorations also need to be evaluated.

Clinical practice:

- ◇ The **PPI** group for this project indicated patients would like to be kept **informed** of the potential **health** implications of different restorative materials and involved in the **decision-making** process.

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Journal article:

[Shaw et al., The health impacts of dental amalgam and alternative restorative materials: a systematic review. Journal of Dentistry 167 \(2026\)](#)

[https://enb.iisd.org/
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mercury-cop6-summary](https://enb.iisd.org/minamata-convention-mercury-cop6-summary)
**Minamata COP-6
Summary Report 3-7
November 2025**

Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility

We are one of two research groups in the UK commissioned by the National Institute of Health and Care Research Policy Research Programme to conduct syntheses of evidence to inform policy development and evaluation across the full policy remit of the DHSC. The views expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the DHSC.

References

1. NHS Business Services Authority. In the spotlight. Article 2: Inlays and Onlays. 2019.
2. National Dental Epidemiology Programme for England. Oral health survey of adults attending general dental practices 2018. London: Public Health England; 2020.
3. Houston MC. Role of mercury toxicity in hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and stroke. J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich). 2011;13(8):621-7.
4. Saturday A. Journal of Environment and Health Science Mercury and its Associated Impacts on Environment and Human Health: A Review Citation: Saturday, A. Mercury and its Associated Impacts on Environment and Human Health: A Review. 2018:37-43.
5. UN Environmental Programme. Phasing down the use of dental amalgam 2025
6. International Institute for Sustainable Development. Summary report 3–7 November 2025,, Minamata Convention on Mercury. United Nations Environment Programme; 2024.